

CONSEQUENCES OF ADDITION OF POLYPROPYLENE FIBRE ON CHARACTERISTICS OF CONCRETE

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Abstract: The study have presented effect of polypropylene fibre on properties of concrete. One of the most vital building materials used nowadays is concrete. Concrete's durability is primarily responsible for its significance. . Concrete can resist a lot of wear and tear, unlike other building materials. It is used to construct buildings, bridges, highways, and other constructions. But apart from all the advantages, Low tensile strength and low fracture strain are two drawbacks of plain concrete. To overcome all these issues, most of the time, these flaws are fixed by concrete reinforcement and out of all the fibre reinforcement is one of the options. For this study, polypropylene fibre has been used. Polypropylene fibre is a polymer material that is light in weight having high strength and corrosion resistance. The tensile strength, flexural strength, compressive strength are discussed as per previous literature review. Also mode of change of failure with inclusion of polypropylene fibre is examined and discussed in detail. With the addition of Polypropylene fibre, the conclusions which were drawn are: Polypropylene fibre have improved various properties of concrete. Polypropylene fibres in concrete mix have improved serviceability of concrete structures by reducing width of cracks that is reduced by stress distribution. However, Upto certain amount of polypropylene fibre properties are improved, after that percentage results reverse. Also it has been found that concrete properties like compressive strength, flexure strength etc also gets increased upto certain limit but after that, results gets reversed. It has also been found that Tensile strength have also exhibited improved with addition of fibre due to crack bridging mechanism. Also mode of failure has changed from brittle to ductile mode.

Keywords: Concrete, Crack mechanism, Polypropylene fibre, Fibre Reinforced concrete

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a material that serves a variety of functions well. An example of a building material is concrete, which is created using cement, water, and earth. It serves a variety of functions and is robust and long-lasting. Construction projects are among the most frequent uses of concrete. Along with bridges and highways, concrete is used to construct walls, floors, and ceilings. Buildings can also be made to be more sustainable and energy-efficient with its help. The most popular varieties of concrete are cement, mortar, and concrete, though there are many others. Slaked lime and calcium oxide combine to form the hardening component known as calcium silicate hydrate, which is used to make cement. Clay, sand, water, and Portland cement are the usual ingredients in mortar. Portland cement is combined with large aggregates, like gravel or stone, to create concrete.

In manufacturing, including the creation of cars and trucks, concrete is also used. Manufacturers can increase the tensile strength and damage resistance of their products by utilising concrete.

One of the most vital building materials used nowadays is concrete. It is used to construct buildings, bridges, highways, and other constructions. Sidewalks and other pedestrian paths can also be built with concrete.

Concrete's durability is primarily responsible for its significance. Concrete can resist a lot of wear and tear, unlike other building materials. It can survive various forms of weather, including earthquakes, floods, and others. This makes it an extremely trustworthy building material. Other advantages of concrete exist as well. It is simple to combine and pour, for instance. It can therefore be applied to a broad range of construction projects. Moreover, compared to other building materials, it is inexpensive. Concrete is a very functional and affordable building material. The usage of plain cement concrete in building is constrained by its high compressive strength and low tensile strength. When good compressive strength, weight, and tensile stresses are the primary criteria, plain concrete is employed.

Just before beginning any masonry or R.C.C. work directly on the excavated earth, PCC is used to create a level surface. Other terms for PCC include cement concrete and binding concrete.

Types of concrete on the basis of casting:-

There are numerous varieties of concrete, each having special qualities of its own. Cast-in-place, precast, and pre-stressed concrete, which are the three most popular varieties.

Cast-in-place concrete: It is the most typical type of concrete used in construction. It is created by pouring a cement, water, and aggregate (stones, boulders, etc.) combination into a mould and shaping it into the desired shape. After the mixture has been cast, it is put into a machine that vibrates it until it solidifies. In order to finish the concrete as rapidly as possible, this process is typically carried out outside.

Precast concrete: Precast concrete and cast-in-place concrete are similar in that both are created by pouring a cement, water, and aggregate mixture into the required shape. However, precast concrete is often created in factories before being transported to the job site. Precast concrete has several restrictions compared to cast-in-place concrete because of this, but it also makes planning and carrying out construction projects easier.

Pre-stressed concrete: Pre-stressed concrete is a type of concrete where the concrete is first compressed before the external load is applied, allowing the desired amount of stress from the external load to be counteracted during the service time. High-strength steel wire or alloys (referred to as "tendons") that are positioned in the concrete section cause this initial compression.

Properties of plain cement concrete:-

1. *Compressive strength:* PCC has a compressive strength of 200 to 500 kg/cm².
2. *Tensile strength:* Concrete made with ordinary cement has a tensile strength of 50 to 100 kg/cm².
3. *Density:* Concrete has a density that ranges from 2200 Kg/m³ to 2400 Kg/m³.
4. *Durability:* It is more enduring.

With its great compressive strength, low cost, and accessibility of raw materials, concrete is extensively employed in structural engineering. The most popular building material, concrete, offers a number of advantageous qualities, including great compressive strength, flexibility, and durability in typical weather conditions. Concrete is also fragile and tension-sensitive. But apart from all the advantages, Low tensile strength and low fracture strain

are two drawbacks of plain concrete for instance, shrinkage and cracking, poor toughness, excessive brittleness, poor shock resistance, and so on, that limit its applicability.

It is commonly known that the following factors lead to fractures:

- *plastic shrinkage*: which results from the loss of water in the plastic state due to evaporation.
- *chemical shrinkage*: (smaller volume of hydrates than cement and water) and auto desiccation (decrease in the pore water due to hydration) are two types of autogenous shrinkage.
- *thermal contraction (or thermal shrinkage)*: due to the decrease in temperature after setting .
- *drying shrinkage*: due to the loss of water to the environment in the hardened state .
- *carbonation shrinkage*: volume reduction due to the reaction of hydrated cement paste with CO₂ in the presence of moisture. shrinkage from carbonation that occurs when moisture-containing cement paste reacts with CO₂ to lose volume.

Most of the time, these flaws are fixed by concrete reinforcement and out of all the fiber reinforcement is one of the options. In order to combat the fractures, a fighting method that combines concrete with discrete fibres has become popular in recent years. Fiber-reinforced concrete is one (FRC) due to its superior flexural-tensile strength, splitting resistance, impact resistance, good permeability, and frost resistance, has been employed successfully in construction.

The commonly used building material in construction industry is concrete. Concrete is cause of pollution to environment and have also various disadvantages. The drawbacks in concrete are related to its strength i.e its weak in tension and doesn't arrest crack formation. To overcome these disadvantages, fibre is added in concrete. Since the last fifty years, fibre in concrete has been used to alter the typical concrete's qualities to meet needs. Certain qualities of concrete are improved with the addition of fibre, while others are reduced. Slump value typically declines. A fall in slump value does not always imply a reduction in workability. Commonly used fibres are steel fibre, carbon fibre, PVC, PVA fibre, glass fibre etc.

1.3 Effect of length of fibre on function

Effect of fibre on properties of concrete depends on various factors, one of them is length of fibre. Whether its short fibre or long fibre, function of fibre varies as per that. That means short fibres (>30mm) connects small cracks whereas long fibres connects large cracks. This way fibres works in concrete mixture. Also long fibre are utilised in less quantity whereas short fibres are used in more amount, this is because long fibre in more amount can cause lumps and can reduce properties of concrete. Figure 1 shows the effect of length of fibre on properties concrete [13].

Fig. 1: Effect of length of fibre on function [13]

1.4 Mechanism of failure

Mode of failure in concrete is brittle that means in concrete there is sudden failure and this problem is solved by inclusion of fibre in concrete. When fibre is added, fibre form bond with concrete mix and when loads exceed to maximum load carrying capacity of concrete, fibre carry load for sometime. This means concrete doesn't break suddenly, it take time. Hence failure mode changes to ductile mode [5].

Figure 2: effect of concrete on mode of failure [5]

2 Effect of polypropylene fibre on properties of concrete

2.1 Shrinkage

When the water in air evaporates, the volume change is termed as drying shrinkage. It can't be avoided as it's harmful for concrete structure. In drying shrinkage moisture is evaporated from surface and pores of concrete. To avoid crack formation in concrete due to drying shrinkage polypropylene fibre is used. In high performance concrete, superplasticizer are added to ensure workability as w/c is low. For the chemical process of hydration to take place, amount of water is insufficient compared to cement amount, negative pressure (tensile) is generated as water from fine pores is utilised in chemical process. The whole phenomenon results decrease in volume of concrete that in not even in harden state and the phenomenon is known as autogenous shrinkage pf concrete. For high strength concrete, autogenous shrinkage plays important role in total shrinkage [1]. Figure 3 have mentioned stresses that are generated due to shrinkage in concrete mix where line 1 represents tensile strength of concrete mix with polypropylene fibre and line 2 represents tensile strength without polypropylene fibre [2].

When the concrete mix is in semi liquid state i.e. after few hours of casing, cracks occur because of plastic shrinkage. Cracks due to plastic shrinkage are difficult to study as material change their properties w.r.t. time and that change is more rapid in starting few hours. Damage due to plastic shrinkage can be present by knowing origin of plastic shrinkage. Chemical shrinkage doesn't have significant effect on plastic shrinkage as it takes place in starting after placing of concrete. It's observed that cracks due to plastic shrinkage occur after drying of concrete surface or we can say that if bleeding water rises to surface at greater rate than evaporation, plastic shrinkage takes place[3]. Cracks due to plastic shrinkage are reduced by reducing rate of evaporation.

From previous studies it's observed that polypropylene fibre significantly decreases the percentage of drying shrinkage in concrete. And when polypropylene fibre is present in concrete mix, tensile stress near and around cracked areas are transferred and crack propagation is arrested

Polypropylene fibre in concrete mix reduces size of crack area due to plastic shrinkage , plastic shrinkage is also affected by screeding rate. About 95% of plastic shrinkage crack area is reduced at higher screeding rate[4]. When fresh concrete surfaces are exposed to environment, plastic shrinkage takes place due to consolidation, tensile stresses and cracks are generated have negative impact on integrity and durability of concrete surfaces. When PP fibre is added in concrete mixture and plastic shrinkage forces start generating, PPF these forces and stabilise structure at early stage. This way PP fibre reinforced concrete have improved settlement of cracks and negative effect of vibrations[4]. Effect of polypropylene fibre on bleeds is represented in figure 4 [4].

Fig. 3: stresses due to shrinkage [2]

Figure 4: bleeding test results [4]

2.2 Compressive strength

To examine effect of polypropylene fibre on compressive strength, percentage of fibre is changes by weight of cement or volume. Three mixes were prepared i.e. A, B and C, results concluded that increase is upto 16%, 11% and 7% for A, B and C mixes respectively. 0.2% of PPF is determined as optimum value. After 0.2% of polypropylene fibre, compressive strength continues decreases. Compressive strength increases due to bonding between concrete components and fibre is concrete mix whereas decrease after 0.2% of polypropylene fibre may be because of lump formation by excess amount of fibre that decreases load carrying capacity and crack strength. Another reason may be negative effect of higher amount of fibres on process of hydration [6].

Table 1: Effect on compressive strength [6]

specimen	fcu (Mpa) 7-DAYS	Fcu (Mpa) 28-days
CU-0_A	21.9	33.4
CU-0.1_A	23.65	37.33
CU-0.2_A	23.76	38.8
CU-0.3_A	23.78	35.6
CU-0.5_A	20.2	33.3
CU-0.0_B	18.2	28.93
CU-0.1_B	20.1	30.4
CU-0.2_B	21.9	32
CU-0.3_B	18.3	28.2
CU-0.5_B	13.5	25.4
CU-0.0_C	7.2	20.1
CU-0.1_C	10.5	20.6
CU-0.2_C	12.5	21.45
CU-0.3_C	11.5	20.3
CU-0.5_C	7.6	12.8

2.3 Flexural strength

Flexural strength of concrete mix with addition of polypropylene fibre continues increases with increase in the percentage of fibre. The maximum increase is observed between 0.2-0.3% of PPF. Increase in flexural strength is defined because of improvement in ductility with inclusion of fibre as mode of failure changes with inclusion of fibre from brittle to ductile. Flexural strength increases upto 0.3% of PPF, after 0.3% of PPF flexural strength continues decreases. Also polypropylene fibre have decreased the length of crack area when fibre is added in concrete mix that is further explained as fibre bridge cracks this way fibres reduce width of cracks and enhance resistance against cracking[12].

Figure 5: effect of PPF on flexural strength

2.4 Tensile strength

For concrete, its tensile strength is 10% of its compressive st. Clearly when fibre is added to concrete, tensile properties are improved. In fibre reinforced concrete, fibre reduces crack formation in concrete mix in both hardened and plastic state [11]. From past studies it's concluded that tensile strength increases with increase of polypropylene fibre in concrete matrix and rises upto certain limit after that it decreases. In [12] it's explained that upto 0.36% of polypropylene fibre tensile strength increases upto 16% compared to conventional concrete mix after that results reverse. It's concluded that maximum strength can be achieved by uniformly distributing of fibres and aspect ratio should be carefully selected. Bridging mechanism of fibre is reason for improvement in tensile strength whereas bonding of concrete mix with fibres is not proper at higher amount of polypropylene fibre[12]. Change in failure patten is observed when fibre is added i.e. in FRC after first crack concrete sample doesn't break suddenly in-fact large cracks observed after maximum loading, this explains change in failure behaviour from brittle to ductile.

Figure 6: effect of PPF on tensile strength

2.5 Workability

From past studies it's concluded that addition of polypropylene fibre have negative impact on workability. This effect continues decreases with increase in percentage of

polypropylene fibre[10]. In case of self compacting concrete (SCC) results observed with addition of polypropylene fibre are same (negative) [8]. Also in many studies when workability is reduced with addition of polypropylene fibre, water reducing admixture is added to mix at low w/c [7]. In another study, multifilament PPF were utilised and fresh properties were determined for different mixes that are 3,6,9,12kg/m³. In all mixes fibres were homogeneous mixed and it was observed that air content in all mixes show rise with rise in percentage of fibre but fresh properties were not affected too much[9]. In another study, workability have exhibit same results as discussed above i.e fibre addition have resulted in reduction in workability due to random distribution of fibres in mixture as air is entrapped when fibres are added. It's concluded that range of workability is medium [10].

Figure 9: effect on slump value [12]

3.6 Permeability

To determine moisture content permeability is measured. In previous studies its mentioned if concrete samples are not properly operated, it may affect permeability and when conventional concrete samples are compared with fibre reinforced concrete, samples with fibre exhibit less permeability. The reason behind this is crack bridging mechanism of fibres by which fibres inhabit crack growth and it's concluded that permeability is the reason behind diffusion of chlorine ions in concrete matrix [13].

3 Conclusion

Polypropylene fibre have improved various properties of concrete and is used in various fields of engineering because of applications of polypropylene fibre. In construction industry, polypropylene fibre is used in construction of pavements, footpaths, its also used in interior design i.e in architectural engineering. From above study it's concluded that

- . Polypropylene fibre in concrete mix have improved serviceability of concrete structures by reducing width of cracks that is reduced by stress distribution.
- . Upto certain amount of polypropylene fibre properties are improved, after that percentage results reverse.
- . In maximum cases workability have reduced with addition of fibre, this is because of random distribution of fibres due to which air is entrapped and air content increases.
- . In some cases water reducing admixtures are added to avoid negative impact of polypropylene fibre on workability.
- . Compressive strength increases upto certain amount after that results reverse, increase is due to good bonding between mix and fibre and decrease in compressive strength at high amount is due to lump formation by fibres in mix.
- . Flexural strength is improved with inclusion of fibre in concrete because of improvement in durability that is because fibre bridge cracks and increases load bearing capacity.
- . Delay in degradation of concrete structure is observed when fibres are present in concrete by reducing permeability and shrinking thereby enhancing durability of concrete element.
- . Uniform distribution of fibres are more effective than random distribution of fibres.
- . Tensile strength have also exhibited improved with addition of fibre due to crack bridging mechanism. Also mode of failure is changed from brittle to ductile mode.

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